

Original Article

EFFECTIVE USAGE OF DIGITAL LEARNING RESOURCES: A PANACEA FOR ENHANCING STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN ENUGU EDUCATION ZONE OF ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

This research is a descriptive survey which explored the effective usage of digital learning resources (DLR) by secondary school students of Enugu Education Zone in Enugu State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised the 32 principals of the 32 public secondary schools and 10% of the 1,950 teachers in the zone. A 25 item questionnaire titled 'Effective Usage of Digital Learning Resources: A Panacea for Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (EUDLRPSAPQ) developed by the researcher was used to collect relevant data. Face validity of the instrument was determined by two experts in the department of Educational Management and one from the Department of Mathematics and Computer Science Education (Measurement and Evaluation unit), all from the Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Agbani. Reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha method and an alpha value of 0.85 was obtained showing high reliability of the instrument. Data obtained was analyzed using mean with standard deviation to answer the research questions, while z- test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. Results revealed that principals and teachers rated to a very great extent the usage of digital learning resources (DLR) by secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone in Enugu State, Nigeria. They also rated to a very great extent the factors that facilitate the effective usage of DLR by students. Moreover, principals and teachers did not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent of usage of DLR and on the factors that facilitate the effective usage of DLR in those schools. Based on these findings, it was recommended among other things that teachers should avail themselves of the ICT practical, and as well embrace the new transformational education system. Government should make fund available for the provision of DLRs. Students should also have interest in following the new educational trend.

Keywords: *Effective usage, Digital learning resources, Secondary Schools, Academic Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is undergoing a radical transformation in this 21st century and is driven by the rapid development of Information and Communication technology (ICT). Timotheou, Miliou, Dimitriads,

Sobrino, Giannoutsou, Cachia, MartinezMones and Ioannou (2022) assert that digital technologies have brought changes to the nature and scope of education and led education systems worldwide to adopt strategies and policies for ICT integration. This being

the case, a very important change occurred in the educational system. However, HAWUEI (2024), maintains that the traditional model of classroom – based learning, where teachers deliver lectures and students passively receive information is no longer sufficient to meet the diverse needs and expectations of learners in a globalized and digitalized world. This being the case, there is an urgent need for a shift from the old system of teaching and learning to a new one which may enhance students’ rate of learning and positively influences their academic performance. To buttress this, HUAWEI (2024), reiterates that a new paradigm shift in education is emerging, where learning is more interactive, personalized, collaborative and engaging. This paradigm shift is enabled by the concept of digital classroom which integrates ICT products and resources into learning environment to enhance the teaching and learning experience. This is now being practiced all over the world including Nigeria.

In Nigeria and in other countries of the world for instance, there has been a gradual change of teaching and learning methods from the use of chalk and black board to a digital method in this 21st century. Adamu, (2023) stated that there has been a change from teacher centered traditional method to student centered digital communication method. This new era in education is driven by transformative power of technology and the National Digital Learning Policy have set forth strategic framework to harness the potential of digital learning and ensure its effective implementation across Nigeria’s diverse educational landscape. Continuing, the author noted that the advent of COVID-19 pandemic has not only disrupted traditional modes of education but also has highlighted the urgent need to accelerate our efforts in leveraging digital learning as an alternative means of delivering quality education. Further on this, Timotheuo et al (2022) assert that this issue of integration of ICTs and the design of education system in accordance with current technological trends were emphasized during the COVID-19

pandemic that accelerated the use of digital technologies in education. This tends to create a paradigm shift from the old method of teaching and learning to a new one by improving students’ performance in this era. Moreover, students’ engagement and motivation have generally increased through collaborative learning methods and other key principles that are integrated into the teaching and learning processes. Today, the internet dominates many aspects of our lives. We are used to it that we do not even think about all the areas it touches (Asogwa, 2011). Nowadays, students are the centre of all learning processes and almost all education policies emphasize learner- centre approach with teacher fulfilling specific pedagogical functions while students learn in an internet enabled environment

Internet environment became more prominent during the period of COVID-19 Pandemic. With wide spread lockdowns and social distancing measures in place, people increasingly relied on the internet for various aspects of their lives. Schools and universities shifted to online learning making the internet a crucial tool for students to access the educational resources and as well participate in virtual learning for their academic programmes. During this period in Nigeria, the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) recognized the critical role of technology in mitigating the impact of the pandemic and ensuring continuity of education for both urban and marginalized populace (Adamu, 2023). The author also maintains that the National Digital Learning Policy gives a comprehensive response to the demands of the policy makers, school administrators and teachers in their quest to equip learners with the necessary skills for an ever changing world. This policy has risen to the challenges of the rapidly evolving 21st century learning landscape which is characterized by changing pedagogical and technological approaches that are mainly anchored on the digitalized method of teaching and learning.

Digitalized teaching and learning refer to the integration of digital technologies into the educational process to enhance teaching and learning experiences.

Dailey et al in (Pate, 2023), describe digitalized teaching and learning as a state of policy framework that supports full and part time access to online learning. It also eliminates seat time requirement and supports expanded broadband access. The authors state that the digital learning contributes to students' access to devices such as smartphones and tablets. They also assert that it makes a shift to digital instructional materials. This can however bring about pedagogical practices and use of technology which will naturally motivate the students to learning while internet and social networking tools can provide opportunities for students to find information, collect their own materials, communicate, create meaning and evaluate the final outcome. Batchelder in Pate (2023) was of the opinion that student self-directed learning practices will create a comfortable learning environment. Pate (2019), then defines digital learning as an effective teaching method used to enhance students' learning experiences. It emphasizes a high quality teaching experience and provides access to challenging contents, feedback through formative assessment and self-learning opportunity at students own pace in a digital classroom.

A digital classroom is a classroom that uses computers and tablets, the internets and educational software to enhance student learning. However, digital classroom can be an extension of the physical classroom that provides additional opportunities for collaboration and research. The digital classroom can also be a student only virtual classroom for synchronous instruction and collaboration (Thompson, 2024). The author also states that a digital classroom must utilize technology to encourage and facilitate collaboration, promote self-study and reinforcement and drive learning discussion in a digital medium. The digital classroom can provide easy access to information resources and forums to discuss class topics. Students can engage with one another in real time as well as get feedback. A digital classroom can also be seen as a classroom that integrates electronic devices such as

smartphones, interactive whiteboards, acoustic devices, computer, internet connections and software to enhance the teaching and learning process (HUAWEI, 2024). For Pate (2019), a digital classroom can be considered as the vital element in promoting and improving the traditional method of teaching and learning. This required a shift from a teacher centered to a student centered environment where the instructor must take on multiple new roles. Hence, the integrating of technology into the classroom is an approach to develop better understanding of basic concepts provided for learning if they are applied approximately using digital learning resources (DLR).

A digital learning resource (DLR) is a learning resource that is facilitated, enabled or mediated by technology. It can involve different methods, such as online classes, social learning, virtual learning, X-reality aids, online exams, and blended learning. This can give learners some control over time, places path and pace of their learning (Adamu, 2023). Digital learning resources (DLR) however, according to Dillon (2023) are resources that help students learn in a digitalized environment. They are aimed at increasing student achievement while decreasing the workload on teachers and administrators. Continuing, Dillon stated that technology in classroom has become increasingly prevalent as many secondary schools move to one to-one device model as each student is issued with a laptop or tablet upon admission. Moreover, smartphones are becoming more common in many classrooms which allow the teacher to interact with digital learning resources during their presentation of new contents. This has created an immense impact on how students learn information and invariably, can lead to students' academic improvement. . Digital learning resources can also be seen as resources that can help students to improve their learning abilities. According to Camilleri (2017), digital learning resources are resources used for education in many ways and are implemented in different forms.

Camilleri (2017), further reiterated that in traditional classrooms, digital learning resources are used as supplement to the primary course content, while in virtual learning, the digital resources actually make up what is in the content of the class. For Kenchakkanawar in Bhavsar (2021), digital learning resources are resources which require computer access or any electronic product that delivers a collection of data be it referring to full text bases, electronic journals, image collection, and other multimedia products and numerical, graphical or time based, as a commercially available title has been published with an aim to being marketed. These may be delivered on CD ROM or Tape, via internet and so on.

There are only two types of digital learning resources, Bhavsar (2021) identified them as online digital learning resources and off line digital learning resources. The author further states that these digital learning resources can be differentiated by primary sources of information, reference sources, online database, libraries and subject gateways, meta resources, e-books etc. Moreover, the author said that the digital learning resources can be categorized as born digital and digitalized resources categorized by open access digital resources and commercial digital resources. The author maintains that digital learning resources can be categorized on the basis of format like, **.jpeg**, **.wav**, **.doc**, **.pdf** etc. All these digital learning resources are available through publishers, vendors, aggregators, library consortium etc. Hence, the effective usage of these digital resources by students can enhance their academic performance.

A number of factors can facilitate the effective usage of digital learning by students. These factors according to Ojo and Olakulehin (2019) can be classified into four main categories: infrastructure, cultural, pedagogical and economic factors. These factors affect the usage of digital learning resources by students either positively or negatively. The ability of students to make use of different learning resources is dependent on the availability of these factors. This

is evidenced by the research conducted by Azimi, Razak and Ghazalli (2018). Wei, Li and He (2019), studied the influencing factors of college students' use of online learning platform from the perspective of customers. Their findings revealed that students' perceptions of social media usefulness and ease of use are two critical factors influencing their use of social media as learning tools. Azimi, Razak and Ghazali (2018), on their own are of the opinion that factors like perceived usefulness, ease of use and learning environment influenced students' satisfaction with e-learning platform. Alhussain (2020), also asserts that social media platforms affect students' educational achievement through interactions between students and lecturers.

Studies have shown that usage of digital learning resources by students have increased their performance drastically. Vogt et al in Kairova and Gabdullinia (2020) reported that digital technologies have a positive impact on teaching and learning in schools. They added that this was exemplified when using a series of digital games in teaching mathematics to elementary school children. Badia et al in Khanvirava and Gabdullinia on their own identified some factors influencing the ideas of primary and secondary school teachers about the benefits of using digital technologies in their teaching practices. Invariably, this will enhance students; academic performance in all ramifications. Similarly, studies done by Adeniran (2019) on the influence of digital learning resource on the students' academic performance showed that digital learning resources have the potentials to increase students' academic performance by providing them with appropriate and up to date information items. In another dimension, Nwankwo and Ukeh (2023), reported that incorporating gamification into the teaching strategy improves the overall learning experience leading to heightened engagement, motivation, social interaction and academic achievement. However, the authors confirmed that students who were taught computer processing unit using the gamification

performed better academically compared to those taught using expository method.

The knowledge of ICT has been emphasized as the effective vehicle for teaching and learning. Hence, Zamani and Karan (2011) opine that the use of ICT promotes effective engagement of the learners, enhancement of learning, ease the use of teaching methods and materials to respond to students' interests and needs. Mahdinejad and Amoi (2011), in their study on tertiary education institutions reported that 54, 2 % of the colleges lack well equipped computer laboratories. Similarly, Shekari (2010), finds relatively low usage of ICT facilities to advance teaching and learning, which implies that both teachers and students would have limited opportunities and capabilities in using ICT facilities to expand their knowledge and skills in curriculum instruction. Consequently, the quality of education being given to learners would be inadequate reflecting low outcome.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The integration of digital learning resources in secondary education has transformed the learning landscape, offering numerous benefits including enhanced engagement, accessibility and personalization. However, the effective usage of these resources remains a significant challenge in many secondary schools especially in Enugu education zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. Despite the potentials of usage of digital learning resources to enhance academic performance of secondary school students in this zone, it has not been clear to the researcher as whether these resources are available at all in this zone, whether teachers have the knowledge of ICT and whether students have access to these digital learning resources even when they are available in their various schools.

The thrust of this study therefore was to investigate the influence of effective usage of digital learning resources on the academic performance of secondary school students of this zone. However, there were no

empirical evidences to support this claim in Enugu education zone of Enugu state, neither is there any study to the best knowledge of the researcher that has tried to examine the influence of effective usage of digital learning resources on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu zone of Enugu state, Nigeria. The poser therefore is what influence does the effective usage of digital learning resources have on academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu education zone of Enugu state, Nigeria?

PURPOSE OF STUDY:

The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of effective usage of digital learning resources on the academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu education zone of Enugu state, Nigeria. Specifically the study investigated the;

1. Extent of usage of digital learning resources by secondary school students in Enugu Education zone,
2. Factors that facilitate the effective usage of digital learning resources in secondary schools in Enugu education zone of Enugu state, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS;

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What are the extent of usage of digital learning resources by secondary school students of Enugu education Zone?
2. What factors facilitate the effective usage of digital learning resources by secondary school students in Enugu education zone of Enugu state, Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES:

The following hypotheses guided the study;

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent of usage of digital learning resources by secondary school students of Enugu Education Zone.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the factors that facilitate the effective usage of digital learning resources by secondary school students in Enugu education zone of Enugu state, Nigeria.

METHOD:

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study, using researcher’s developed instrument tagged effective usage of digital learning resources; a panacea for students’ academic performance questionnaire (EUDLRPSAPQ). The instrument was a twenty five (25) item questionnaire validated by three experts. Two of these experts are from the Department of Educational Management and one is from the department of Mathematics and Computer Education (Measurement and Evaluation option), all from faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Agbani. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method and an alpha value of 0.85 was found indicating high reliability of the instrument for the study. The respondents consist of all 32 principals of the 32 public secondary schools in the area and 10 percent of the 1,950 teachers which amounted to 195 teachers. The instrument for the

study was then administered to the respondents which was later collected. Some copies of the instrument administered to teachers were lost and some were badly filled. The whole 32 copies of the instruments administered to the principals were retrieved, giving 100 percent return rate. Out of 195 copies of the instrument administered to teachers, 172 copies were retrieved giving 88 percent return rate. Any rating between 2.50 and above was regarded as great extent (GE), while any rating below 2.50 was regarded as low extent (L). The data collected were analyzed using mean with standard deviation. z- Test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS:

Research Question 1: What are the extent of usage of digital learning resources by secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviation of principals and teachers on the extent of usage of digital learning resources by secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone:

Items	Principals			Teachers			Aggregate			
	Mean	SD	Deci sion	Mean	SD	Deci sion	Mean	SD	Deci sion	
1	Audio lectures	3.8	0.09	VGE	3.8	0.11	VGE	3.8	1.33	VGE
2	Video lectures	3.5	0.09	VGE	3.5	0.12	VGE	3.5	0.40	VGE
3	Online quizzes	3.6	0.41	VGE	3.6	0.23	VGE	3.6	0.12	VGE
4	Online textbooks	3.5	0.11	VGE	3.5	0.11	VGE	3.5	0.31	VGE
5	Online discussion forms	3.9	0.31	VGE	3.7	0.51	VGE	3.9	0.12	VGE
6	Online assessment	3.7	0.33	VGE	3.6	0.50	VGE	3.8	0.13	VGE
7	E-book libraries	3.8	0.21	VGE	3.7	0.17	VGE	3.9	1.12	VGE
8	Interactive white boards	3.7	0.11	VGE	3.5	0.04	VGE	3.7	1.04	VGE
9	Educational games	3.5	0.01	VGE	3.6	0.51	VGE	3.8	1.11	VGE
10	Video conferencing	3.9	0.13	VGE	3.7	0.31	VGE	3.6	0.45	VGE
11	Digital textbooks	3.8	0.16	VGE	3.8	0.12	VGE	3.8	0.50	VGE
12	Virtual laboratories	3.7	1.04	VGE	3.5	0.13	VGE	3.7	0.11	VGE
GRAND MEAN		3.7	0.31	VGE	3.6	0.23	VGE	3.7	0.54	VGE

N₁=32 N₂=172 NB: VGE: Very Great Extent, GE: Great extent, LE: Low Extent, VLE: Very Low extent

From table 1, the grand mean for principals was 3.7 and that of teachers was 3.6 while the aggregate grand mean was 3.7. This result indicates that both

principals and teachers rated to a very great extent the usage of all the available digital learning resources. The standard deviation value (0.54) was small, indicating little or no extreme scores. Hence, the mean scores were reliable.

Research Question 2: What factors facilitate the effective usage of digital learning resources by secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation ratings of principals and teachers on the factors that facilitate the effective usage of digital learning resources by secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone:

Items	Principals			Teachers			Aggregate			
	Mean	SD	Decision	Mean	SD	Decision	Mean	SD	Decision	
13	Availability of computers	3.4	0.90	GE	3.3	0.88	GE	3.4	0.33	GE
14	Availability of smartphones	3.3	1.26	GE	3.4	0.95	GE	3.4	0.35	GE
15	Reliable internet connectivity	3.2	1.06	GE	3.1	0.06	GE	3.3	0.52	GE
16	Well-equipped ICT laboratories	3.4	1.14	GE	3.3	0.15	GE	3.4	0.21	GE
17	Power supply and backup system	3.3	1.04	GE	3.4	0.12	GE	3.3	0.33	GE
18	Provision of security policies	3.4	0.90	GE	3.4	0.88	GE	3.4	0.33	GE
19	Students digital literacy	2.9	0.85	GE	3.1	0.93	GE	3.3	0.44	GE
20	Teachers' ability to access ICT tools	3.4	0.99	GE	3.0	0.11	GE	3.2	0.35	GE
21	Teachers' guidance and support	3.3	0.26	GE	2.8	0.95	GE	3.3	0.35	GE
22	Effective integration of digital learning resources into lesson plans.	3.2	0.06	GE	3.1	0.06	GE	3.3	0.52	GE
23	Students' access to digital learning devices at home.	2.9	0.14	GE	3.0	0.15	GE	3.3	0.21	GE
24	Students' interest in the usage of digital learning resources	3.4	0.04	GE	3.3	0.12	GE	3.4	0.33	GE

25	Parental support on students' engagement in the usage of digital learning resources	3.0	0.11	GE	2.7	0.33	GE	3.2	0.12	GE
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GRAND MEAN	0.67	GE	3.1	0.44	GE	3.3	0.36	GE
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N₁=25 N₂=242 NB:VGE: Very Great Extent, GE: Great extent, LE: Low Extent, VLE: Extent Very Low

From table 2, the grand mean for principals was 3.2 and that of teachers was 3.1 while the aggregate grand mean was 3.3. This result indicates that both principals and teachers rated the factors that facilitate effective usage of digital learning resources in the

Table 3: z-test analysis of the differences in the mean rating scores of principals and teachers on the effective usage of digital learning resources by secondary school students in Enugu Education zone.

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	z-calculated	z-critical	Remark
Principals	25	3.7	0.31	0.88	1.96	Not significant (Do not reject null hypothesis)
Teachers	265	3.6	0.23			

From table 3, z-calculated (0.88) is less than z-critical (1.96). Hence, at .05 significant level, the mean ratings of the two groups (principals and teachers) do not differ significantly. Consequently, hypothesis one is not rejected as stated, implying that principals and teachers did not differ significantly on the usage of digital learning resources and how it influences the academic performance of students.

Hypothesis 2

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	z-calculated	z-critical	Remark
Principals	25	3.2	0.67	0.62	1.96	Not significant (Do not reject null hypothesis)
Teachers	265	3.1	0.44			

From table 4, z-calculated (0.62) is less than z-critical (1.96). Hence, at .05 significant level, the mean ratings of the two groups (principals and teachers) do

School to a great extent.Z the standard deviation value (0.36) was small, indicating little or no extreme scores. Thus, the mean scores were reliable.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the usage of digital learning resources and how it influences the academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone.

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the factors that facilitate effective usage of digital learning resources in schools.

Table 4: z-test analysis for the mean rating scores of principals and teachers on the factors that facilitated the effective usage of digital learning resources by secondary school student

not differ significantly. Consequently, hypothesis two is not rejected as stated, indicating that principals and teachers did not differ significantly on the factors that

facilitate effective usage of digital learning resources in schools.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

With the mean ratings of 3.7 and 3.6 for principals and teachers respectively, the researcher found out that both the principals and teachers are of the opinion that digital learning resources (DLR) are effectively used to a very great extent by secondary school students of Enugu Education zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. This finding is in consonance with the finding of Vogt et al in Kairoviva & Gabdullina (2020) that digital learning technologies have a positive impact on teaching and learning in schools. Adeniran (2019) in supporting this assertion also said that digital learning resources have the potentials to increase students' academic performance by providing them with appropriate and up to date information items. Generally speaking, effective usage of digital learning resources (DLR) in secondary schools in Enugu education zone of Enugu State, Nigeria has been proven to enhance students' academic performance.

The factors that facilitate effective usage of digital learning resources in secondary schools in Enugu education zone of Enugu State, Nigeria were also rated to a great extent by both principals and teachers. This finding is in line with that of Azimi et al (2018), Wei et al (2019), which stress that factors like perceived usefulness, ease of use and learning environment influence students' satisfaction with e-learning platform. The finding of this study is also in consonance with that of Murari et al (2022) which assert that perceived enjoyment and system quality

REFERENCES

Adamu A (2023), National digital learning policy. *Federal Ministry of Education* Pp1-62
Adeniran, P. (2013). Usage of electronic resources by undergraduates at the Redeemer University Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science* 5 (10), 319-324

have significant impact on the perceived usefulness and ease of online learning system. The finding of this study is also in line with that of Wei et al (2019) which assert that Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) and other factors significantly affected students' attitude and intentions to use online learning platforms.

CONCLUSION

Digital learning resource is now trending in many institutions across the globe. Government of Enugu State is not left out in this novel plan. Students are also eager to embrace this paradigm shift from the traditional method of classroom based teaching and learning to the new method that is technologically driven.

Both principals and teachers opine that effective usage of digital learning resources greatly enhanced students' academic performance'

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been made:

- 1.Principals should encourage teachers and students to embrace this new and radical transformation in the education system.
- 2.Teachers should avail themselves of the opportunities of practical exposures to ICTs.
- 3.Government should make funds available for provision of digital learning resources.
- 4.Students should be more interested this new educational trend.
- 5.Parents should encourage and support their children on the usage of digital learning resources.

Alhussain, T. (2020). Students' perceptions of social network platforms use in higher education:A qualitative Research. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer scienceand Engineering*.

Asogwa, B.E (2011). Digitalization of archival collections in Africa for scholarship Communication: issues, strategies and

- challenges. *Library philosophy and practices* <https://www.webpages.uidaho.edu/~mbonline/asogwa.htm4>
- Azmmi, F.S., Razak, N.A. & Ghazali, A.R. (2018). Digital learning platform and students' satisfaction: Regression Analysis. *Journal of International Business Economics and Entrepreneurship*. Bhavsar, S.R. (2021). What are digital resources? Discuss what different types are and how Libraries are using them for providing teaching, learning, research support. *Centre for Library and management Studies. Sir Dorabji Memorial Institute of Social Science, Murambai*.
- Camileri, H.C. (2017). Digital learning resources in education. *Lambert Academy Publishing*.
- Dillon, A. (2023). Digital learning resources. Definition, types and examples. *Study.com*
- Huawei, H.C. (2024). What is digital classroom? [http://e.huawei.com/eu/knowledge/2024/industries/commercial market/what is a digital classroom?](http://e.huawei.com/eu/knowledge/2024/industries/commercial-market/what-is-a-digital-classroom?)
- Kairova, I.V. & Gbdullina, E.U (2020). The use of digital learning resources in the implementation of individual education route of primary school students. *Federal University. Kazan, Russia*. Proceedings IFTE, 2020.
- Mahlamba, S., Civilcharram, N., & Ajai, N. (2018). The perception of students about the use of social media as an alternate learning platform. *International Conference on Intelligence and Innovative Computing Applications. ICONIC 2018*.
- Mahdinejad, V., & Amoi. M. (2011). Assessment of computer self- efficacy and attitudes towards computers in university students. *Iranian Journal of Higher Education*. 16 (4), 1 102-117.
- Munari, K., & Rai, S. (2022). Students' attitudes and intentions towards online learning in higher education examining the role of individual & system characteristics. *The Online Journal of Distance Education and e- Learning* 10(3) Pp 339-416.
- Ojo, T., & Olakulehin, T. (2019). Digital literacy and e-learning adoption in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*. 14(20), 107-119.
- Pate, S.R. (2019). Effect of digital learning resources on academic achievement of secondary Students www.researchgate.net/publication/339898982
- Shekari, A. (2010). The effect of using ICT on teaching and learning processes in university Academics. *Iranian Journal of Higher Education Curriculum* 1(2), 57 -89.
- Thompson, S. (2024). Kaltura blog [corp.kaltura.com/blog-digital classroom](http://corp.kaltura.com/blog-digital-classroom).
- Timotheou, S., Miliou, O., Dimitriads, Y., Sobrno, S.V., Giannoutsou, N., Cachia, R., MartinezMones, A & Ioannou, A. (2022). Impact of digital technologies on education and factors influencing schools' digital capacity and transformation. *A literature Review Volume 28 Pp 6695-6726. Physics: Conference Series*. 1345 Jopscience.iop.org
- Wei, Y., Li, J., & He, Y. (2019). Research on the influencing factors of college students' use of online learning platform from perspective of customer. *Journal of*

Zameni, F., & Karadan, S. (2011). Impact of using ICT on learning mathematics, *Iranian Journal*

of Information and Communication Technology in Education Science.1 (1), 23-38.